

China and Cape Verde: How can a small African island state navigate between great powers?

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Introduction

Research on China-Africa relations has, for some time, developed an interest in the concept of agency (Van Staden et al., 2018). The purpose of this body of literature is to explore to what extent African states can mitigate the structural asymmetry of their relationship with China – an asymmetry that is ubiquitous, although even more striking, in the case of small nations. I have already explored this issue in the case of Djibouti and Seychelles (Cabestan, 2020; Cabestan, 2021). Here, I focus on Cape Verde, another small African archipelagic country (4,033 square kilometres) and a former Portuguese colony located in the Atlantic Ocean between 600 and 850 km west of Senegal, where I conducted some fieldwork in June and July 2021.

Partial map of Africa showing location of Cape Verde

As we will see, geography matters; as does population. Spread over nine of the ten volcanic islands constituting the country, its inhabitants amount to around 550,000; and Cape Verde has a very large diaspora – over a million, mainly established in Portugal, France and the United States. History cannot be ignored either. Uninhabited until the Portuguese discovered and took control of it in the 15th century, Cape Verde was at the heart of the Atlantic slave trade until the 19th century, turning it into one of the most ethnically mixed communities in the world: mostly Creole, its population is 57% of African and 43% of European origin.

Since the 19th century, its economy has rapidly declined and its population started to migrate, a decline mitigated by its geostrategic location and, later, tourism. A useful stopover on major shipping and air routes, Cape Verde has become a significant commercial centre. And, since the 1960s, it has been an attractive tourist destination, particularly for surfers (Sal Island). As a result, tourism represents 20-30% of Cape Verde's GDP, while another 20% is made up of remittances sent by the diaspora. Today, Cape Verde remains generally poor with a GDP amounting to US\$2 billion and a GDP per capita of around US\$3,500. The reason is a lack of natural resources (apart from pozzolana – a volcanic ash used as an additive to cement; limestone; and the blue economy – fish and sea food represent 70% of its exports) and a lack of industries – the service sector amounts to 70% of its GDP. Moreover, 90% of the food is imported. As a result, the Covid pandemic hit Cape Verde badly: the economy registered an impressive negative growth rate in 2020 of 14.85%. Its national debt increased in early 2022 to 157% of GDP (\$2.94 billion) before dropping to 143% in November (\$2.86 billion). Today, its external debt represents 75% of GDP with Portugal as its major lender, even if the economy is growing again (+ 7% in 2021 and + 10.5% in 2022).

Finally, politics matters. Having declared independence from Portugal in 1975, one year after the Carnation Revolution, Cape Verde was ruled until 1980 by the African Party for the Independence of Guinea and Cape Verde (*Partido Africano para a Independência da Guiné e Cabo Verde* – PAIGC), created in 1956 by Amílcar Cabral (1924-1973), an open admirer of Mao Zedong. Then, after a coup took place in Bissau, Cape Verde and Guinea Bissau decided to split and go their own way. Even so, Cabral had a lasting impact on the Cape Verde political elites and 1981 saw the creation of the African Party of Independence of Cape Verde (*Partido Africano da Independência de Cabo Verde* – PAICV). Until 1990, Cape Verde was ruled by a Marxist-Leninist, socialist, one-party state close the Soviet Union but also with good relations with the People's Republic of China (PRC): both countries established diplomatic relations in 1976. Moreover, the PAICV and the Chinese Communist Party set up party-to-party relations as early as 1980. Yet, the then party chief and Cape Verde President Aristides Pereira promoted non-alignment, pushed for the country's integration in its regional environment, joining the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) in 1977, and tried to maintain good relations with all the country's partners, including the former colonizer and the West in general. Apart from a few traditional forms of cooperation, China's footprint in Cape Verde was then rather light.

The irony is that the relations between Cape Verde and China started to take off after the end of the Cold War and the democratization of Cape Verde in 1990. In January 1991, the first multi-party elections were held and the newly created opposition party, the Movement for Democracy (*Movimento para a Democracia* – MpD), of liberal and Christian-Democrat inclination, won a majority of the seats

in the National Assembly. At the same time, MpD took control of the presidency. In 2001, the PAICV returned to power, controlling both the National Assembly (until 2016) and the presidency (until 2011). Since then, a well-established, democratic, semi-presidential two-party system (as in Portugal, the Prime Minister is more powerful than the President) has dominated the political stage. Since 2021, the country has entered a period of ‘cohabitation’ between a National Assembly and a government controlled by the MpD, and a PAICV President. Democratization has only partially altered Cape Verde’s foreign policy: while remaining non-aligned and keeping integrated in its regional environment, the country has developed closer relations with the European Union (EU), with which it established a ‘special partnership’ in 2007, and the United States, particularly on security matters (Cook and Husted, 2017). More generally, foreign policy is not a partisan issue.¹

In this article, I will first present the major drivers and features of China’s presence in Cape Verde, particularly its growing activism since the early 2000s, and even more since the launching of the Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) by Xi Jinping in 2013. Then, I will show how the latter has managed to defend its agency in balancing its external relations among its major partners.

The major drivers and features of China’s growing presence in Cape Verde

Between 1976 and the early 2000s

Prior to the 2000s, China’s interest in Cape Verde was small. China’s presence was concentrated in the well-known sectors of Beijing’s activism in the developing world, and particularly in Africa: medical assistance since 1984 and a few infrastructure projects, including, a year later, the country’s National Assembly, located across the road from the Chinese Embassy in Praia, Cape Verde’s capital city.

Being a socialist country until 1991, Cape Verde was then a faithful partner: it had little chance of defecting to Taiwan, a long-standing PRC obsession, particularly in Africa. While Cape Verdean officials regularly visited China, only four visits of Chinese delegations, including Foreign Minister Qian Qichen in 1997, were reported (Cape Verde, 2006).

¹ There are not many scholarly publications on Cape Verde-China relations. The most important author on the issue is probably João Paulo Madeira (Madeira, 2017) whom I met in Praia during my stay there.

National Assembly built with Chinese funding

Other Chinese infrastructure projects were realized in Praia and donated during this period of time, including the Cape Verdean government office building, the Palmarejo housing project, the National Library (1999) and, on the adjacent square, Amílcar Cabral's statue, whose body and coat, according to local opinion, have striking similarities to Mao Zedong's (Interview 1). In addition, in 1996, the Chinese government started to offer scholarships to Cape Verde students.

Before 2000, China also developed contacts with Cape Verde's small military, constituted of two branches, the National Guard and the Coast Guard (1,200 personnel in total). In 1994, China delivered a Harbin Z-9, a medium-lift transport helicopter, to Cape Verde although it is unclear whether it was a gift or a sale (Cape Verde Aircraft List).

China's infrastructure projects then facilitated the settlement of around 3,000 Chinese migrants, often left-behind contractual workers (Carling and Augén, 2008; Horta, 2008).² Most are from Zhejiang although other provinces are represented. Many of them set up shops locally called *Lojas Chines*, not only in Praia or Mindelo, the two main cities, but also in some remote locations where there is little local competition (Holmes, 2011). Some have ended up in Cape Verde after having tried without much success to develop business in Senegal where competition among Chinese is fiercer (Interview 2).

² In 2008, there were already 2,300 Chinese nationals in Cape Verde and around 200 Chinese shops.

Clearly, prior to the 2000s, the Chinese government was just ticking boxes in terms of diplomatic presence and development cooperation in Cape Verde. It did not have any particular interest in the country.

Since the early 2000s

Things started to change in the early 2000s and China's footprint deepened after the launching of the BRI in 2013. Among the drivers of China's growing interest in Cape Verde was the decision to boost its relations with Africa and more specifically the establishment of the Forum of China-Africa Cooperation (FOCAC) in 2000. Cape Verde's participation in its first meeting held in Beijing in October of that year heralded an unprecedented deepening of bilateral cooperation.³ But on the Chinese side, there were other motivations: Cape Verde's strategic location in the Atlantic Ocean. At the turn of the new century, China's great power ambitions and its closely-related plan to build up a blue-water navy as well as a large fishing fleet increased its interest in small island nation-states, especially around the African continent.

To facilitate its contacts with Cape Verde, China used the Macau Forum, an official platform established in 2003 and aimed at reaching out to Portuguese-speaking countries (PSC) (Alden and Alves, 2017). While the Forum has not had much impact on China's relations with major partners such as Brazil or Angola, with small nations like Cape Verde (or Sao Tome and Principe) it has made a difference, and as we will see below, not necessarily for the best.

At the beginning, the BRI did not include West Africa, let alone Cape Verde. But after 2015, this initiative expanded to the whole world, turning into a new weapon to enhance China's global influence to the detriment of the West and particularly the United States. As a result, since the early 2000s, the political relationship between Cape Verde and China has deepened and exchanges of official visits have intensified. Chinese Foreign Minister Wang Yi's visit in 2017 was probably the most significant, highlighting some of Beijing's intentions.

When meeting Wang, the then Prime Minister Ulisses Correia e Silva was quoted by *Xinhua* News Agency as saying that 'Cape Verde regards China as the most reliable partner for African countries and supports China in defending its legitimate rights and playing a greater role in international affairs'. Demonstrating a real convergence of interests, he also declared that 'Cape Verde would also like to maintain communication and coordination with China on issues such as the reform of the United Nations Security Council' (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2017a). On the economic front, while formally endorsing Xi

³ FOCACs are held every three years, alternatively in China and in Africa. The most recent one took place in Dakar in December 2021.

Jinping's Belt and Road Initiative, the Cape Verdean government expressed its hope that China can transfer its expertise and help to develop São Vicente's new maritime Special Economic Zone (SEZ) (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2017b).

For his part, considering Cape Verde as a 'natural extension of the BRI, especially the maritime Silk Road', Wang Yi then made public a long list of sectors in which his country would be willing to be involved, such as Cape Verde's agriculture sector, fishery, marine economy, development of Special Economic Zones, tourism, infrastructure, and human resources development. He also went around São Vicente, openly showing his interest in the development of its SEZ and the adjacent port in Mindelo.

Wang Yi's visit clearly underscored a Chinese ambition to strengthen its economic and geostrategic footprint in this country. Two years later, when meeting visiting Cape Verde Foreign Minister Tavares, Wang stated that China's cooperation with Africa was 'sincere and selfless, and has no geopolitical purposes' (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2019). Nonetheless, as we will see, China's new projects in Cape Verde have rapidly alerted this country's western partners.

To increase its influence among Cape Verde's political elite, the CCP decided in 2009 to establish party-to-party relations with the other ruling party, namely the MpD. Consequently, when Yu Hongjun, the then Deputy Director of the CCP International Liaison Department visited Cape Verde in May 2014, he met both with PAICV and MpD officials (Amaral, 2014).

More infrastructure projects

Since 2000, in order to deepen its footprint and increase its influence in Cape Verde, China has multiplied its infrastructure projects, funded both by grants and loans. The first major gift was the construction of a dam in Santa Cruz on Santiago, Cape Verde's main island where Praia is located (*Barragem de Poilão*). Built in 2006, it cost US\$4.4 million. The same year, with a US\$3million loan, China funded the construction of Agostinho Neto Hospital New Maternity Ward in Praia.⁴

⁴ The loan was attributed by China's Ministry of Commerce, being identified today as coming from the CIDCA (China International Development and Cooperation Agency), an administration created in 2018, cf. <https://www.bu.edu/gdp/chinese-loans-to-africa-database/> [accessed 12 January 2023]. Commitment amount: US\$7.13 million according to AIDDATA, <https://china.aiddata.org/projects/35064/> [accessed 12 January 2023].

More housing projects were completed free of charge in Praia and Mindelo, São Vicente island's main city (Ferreira and Madeira, 2020), its fifth one in early 2022, in close connection with the development of São Vicente Maritime SEZ (Chinese housing project in Cabo Verde, 2022). Later, China built the Military Academy and the National Stadium. Funded by a US\$22 million grant, the latter opened in 2014. China's most recent project has been the construction in the outskirts of Praia of a new campus for the University of Cape Verde, which opened in July 2021. Oversized for Cape Verde, even if the university has decided to attract more overseas students in the future (Interview 1), this university's total cost amounted to 500 million RMB (63 million Euros). On its opening, the then Chinese Ambassador Du Xiacong declared that the campus was the biggest aid project paid for by China in Western Africa (Permanent Secretariat, 2021).

The new University Campus built with Chinese funding

As in many African countries, Chinese projects were realized by provincial state-owned companies, highlighting Beijing's decentralized but coordinated assistance strategy in the developing countries. For example, the National Stadium was built by Shaanxi Huashan (China Top International Engineering Corp) and supervised by Jiangxi Zhongchang Engineering Consultation and Supervision Company; the University was constructed by Jiangsu's Longxin Construction Group (*Longxin jianshe jituan youxian gongsi*) with the help of 150 Chinese workers and 300 local workers. In addition, Longxin signed a two-year maintenance contract with the University (Interview 8).

Huawei

The Chinese government is clearly behind Huawei's involvement in Cape Verde, taking advantage of this country's ambition to become a 'digital nation' and the lack of attractive offers from other partners. While officially a private company, Huawei is *de facto* controlled by the CCP via the company's official trade union. Present since 2009, Huawei has established a close relationship with the country's authorities, leading in September 2019 to the signing of a strategic cooperation agreement between the two. It started training local cadres and technicians in 2014. Huawei first concentrated on developing Cape Verde's e-government capacity (Phase 1), a project funded by a Chinese loan provided by the China Exim Bank (US\$17 million). Then, it reinforced and improved the e-government project (Phase 2), financed by another Exim Bank loan of US\$13 million issued in 2017. Phase 2 involved the upgrading of network infrastructure in schools, public institutions and hospitals, and the installation of computing and storage equipment to support the Government of Cape Verde's overall e-government (EGOV) system. It was completed in 2020.⁵

Huawei's other projects, like 'safe city' (Phase 1 signed in 2017 and Phase 2 signed 2019), are strongly dependent on the technologies it has provided. They also include backing up all government communication systems and providing technology support to e-cloud as well as the medical and education sectors. Moreover, Huawei is the partner of local communication and tech companies such as NOSi, ARME, and CVTelcom. In 2021, company officials complained that Huawei was not earning money and was thinking of withdrawing (Interview 3). Nonetheless, its strong involvement in government projects is likely to convince it to stay as these projects have allowed China to acquire a meaningful influence on Cape Verde's government.

Another method China has used to increase its influence has been active involvement in the international marine cables transiting through Cape Verde. In 2015, Huawei Marine Networks Co. (Huawei Marine) completed upgrades to the section from South Africa to Portugal and Portugal to the United Kingdom of the West Africa Cable System (WACS), using Huawei Marine's leading-edge 100G transmission solution. With the length of the Digital Line Segment (DLS) between South Africa and Portugal beyond 11,450 km, it is one of the longest 100G submarine links in the industry. Commissioned in 2012, WACS is the largest submarine cable directly linking Southern Africa to Europe and is the culmination of investment by eighteen leading international operators and regional carriers. At 14,530 km in total length, WACS initially offered a design capacity of 5.12 Terabits

⁵ <https://www.bu.edu/gdp/chinese-loans-to-africa-database/> [accessed 12 January 2023]. Cf. also <https://china.aiddata.org/projects/52933/> [accessed 12 January 2023].

per second (Tb/s) split among fourteen countries including Cape Verde.⁶

In 2020, Hengtong Group based in Tianjin acquired 81% of Huawei Marine's shares, the remaining 19% being bought by New Saxon 2019 Ltd (UK). Under its new name, HMN Tech (*Huahai tongxin jishu youxian gongsi*), in January 2022 it completed the marine deployment of the Senegal Horn of Africa Regional Express (SHARE) submarine cable system, with landfalls in both Senegal and Cape Verde. The 720km system offers a total design capacity of 16Tbps between Dakar in Senegal and Praia in Cape Verde. Although the project was funded by the Senegal government, China's involvement contributed in putting back Cape Verde on the US government's radar screen (Hillman, 2021).

China and São Vicente Maritime Special Economic Zone (SVMSEZ)

In 2013, in order to further deepen its footprint and influence, the Chinese government grasped the occasion of Cape Verde's plan to establish a maritime Special Economic Zone in São Vicente (SVMSEZ or *Zona Económica Especial Marítima de São Vicente*, ZEEMSV, in Portuguese) to become a key partner of this project, even in its planning stage. The Cape Verde government welcomed this assistance, invoking China's own expertise in creating SEZs (Interview 5). The timing is important: it coincided with the launching of the BRI, especially its maritime dimension.

As a result, in July 2017, the Chinese and Cape Verde governments signed an Economic and Technical Cooperation Agreement (ETCA), which committed grant funding for the SVMSEZ Planning Project. The project has been presented as the outcome of a strategic partnership between the two countries, encouraging private investment and public-private partnerships in maritime activities.

China's Ministry of Commerce partly funded the study for the establishment of the zone (amount unknown); several Chinese delegations came from Shanghai, Shenzhen and Zhoushan to help, and Cape Verdean experts also visited China in 2018. Later, it was reported that it committed US\$17 million for the construction of the zone. This project includes constructing a container terminal, refurbishing Cape Verde Naval Shipyards (*Estaleiros Navais de Cabo Verde*, known as CABNAVE), a state-owned shipyard, and the building of a logistic centre for fish exports in Saragarça, on São Vicente Island (AIDDATA).

According to a law adopted in June 2020, the SVMSEZ should also develop the following strategic sectors: ports, fisheries, tourism, ship repair, shipbuilding

⁶ The other countries are South Africa, Namibia, Angola, Democratic Republic of the Congo, Republic of the Congo, Cameroon, Nigeria, Togo, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Spain (Canary Islands), Portugal and the United Kingdom.

industry and renewable energies. The plan has been to set up a maritime logistics platform in the central Atlantic Ocean region for trans-shipment of cargo and containers, processing, marketing and distribution of maritime products, and making São Vicente an internationally renowned tourist destination equipped with a cruise terminal.

The SVMSEZ Authority was inaugurated in February 2021 and since then, despite the Covid-19 pandemic, some Chinese projects amounting to 900 million Euros have been announced including a Marina Hotel and a Ship Repair Dock.

The Chinese state-owned companies involved in the planning phase give a good indication of China's ambitions: CCCC (China Communication Construction Company), CRBC (China Road and Bridge Corporation), and CHEC (China Harbour Engineering Company). While CCCC and the Cape Verde government signed a Strategic Cooperation Framework Agreement that helped establish the SVMSEZ Authority, CRBC has indicated, since 2013, its intention to build a deep-water port at Mindelo on Porto Grande Bay, as well as a cruise ship terminal, and the possibility of refurbishing Cabnave shipyard on São Vicente Island. It remains to be seen whether this project can be achieved. But building ports in Africa and getting privileged access to them for its Navy have been a key objective of the Chinese government.

To date, there is no fishing agreement between Cape Verde and China (there is one with the EU that has triggered a lot of criticism in Cape Verde which complains about the lack of financial benefit). There is no permanent presence of Chinese fishing boats in Cape Verde but their intrusions in this country's, as well as other Western African nation's, Exclusive Economic Zone is well known, although under-reported. Moreover, Chinese trawlers regularly come to Mindelo for repair at CABNAVE. When I visited Mindelo in July 2021, two of them were under repair in the shipyards (Interview 6).

To be sure, the SVMSEZ is open to all investors: Luxemburg, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal and Spain have all shown interest. Cape Verde's low taxes and financial incentives are attractive. Nevertheless, China has cast a long shadow on this new zone. Its projects for the moment appear only commercial. However, the US and the EU are worried about China's activism in Mindelo, a port city, the strategic location of which has escaped no-one's attention (Interview 7).

More generally, China's presence in Cape Verde has rapidly grown since the early 2000s. To date, according to CARI, it has provided Cape Verde with five loans with a total value of US\$49 million.⁷ Other sources indicate that China has

⁷ <https://www.bu.edu/gdp/chinese-loans-to-africa-database/> [accessed 25 January 2023].

channelled more than US\$200 in development projects in this country (Cabo Verde Politics, 2013). These figures are far from meaningless for a country of this size, demonstrating not only that China leaves no stone unturned in Africa – the continent that has highest number of votes in the United Nations General Assembly – but also that it has developed a special interest in small island states such as Cape Verde, Seychelles, Comoros and Mauritius, as part of its maritime BRI.

Cape Verde's agency

It is clear that China has taken advantage of Cape Verde's multiple development needs to deepen its footprint and increase its influence in this country. Nonetheless, all the projects in which China and Chinese companies have been involved corresponded to a specific request from the Cape Verdean government. And in several cases, the latter has been able to demonstrate its agency, turning down some Chinese projects or balancing China's growing presence by co-operating with other partners, especially the EU, Spain and Portugal, and for security matters, the United States.

The quasi-failure of the Macau casino project

This is an old project. In 2007, Macau Investor, David Chow Kam Fai (周錦輝), then Cape Verde's Honorary Consul in Macau and Legend (澳門勵駿創建有限公司) CEO, made public for the first time his intention not only to build a hotel and a casino in Praia but also to set up a bank in Cape Verde. This project fitted well with China's plan to use Macau as a platform to reach out to Portuguese-speaking countries and was most probably approved by Beijing.

An agreement between the Cape Verde government, Praia municipality, and Legend was signed in 2014. It included the construction of a bridge to an island where a former leprosy colony was located, two hotels, a casino, a marina and a convention centre. The investment amounted to \$300 million and work started in 2016, due to be completed in 2021. Then, in February 2018, Chow applied to set up a bank: the Sino-Atlantic Bank. His declared objective was to contribute to the development of the financial system of the Republic of Cape Verde, by supporting small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the country, as well as by facilitating local and international payments. A year later, Chow proposed changing the contract to first complete Phase 1 of the project for a US\$100, which the Cape Verdean parties accepted (Interview 4). However, in November 2020, Bank Cape Verde, the country's central bank, refused to register Chow's bank arguing that the application of Legend Globe Investment, Chow's business group, did not include 'all the necessary information and documents', including the identification of the founding shareholders, the information on qualified holdings, the management

model, the analysis of the project's viability and the Sino-Atlantic Bank's company charter (Moura, 2020). Actually, the Cape Verdean government suspected money laundering activities from this new bank and, as a result, this project triggered much opposition in the country. Moreover, it is understood that the US Embassy gave the local authorities information that convinced them to turn down Chow's plan (Interview 4).

The failure of the bank project had a negative impact on the hotel and casino project. When I visited Cape Verde in June-July 2021, only one building, still empty, and the bridge to the island, had been completed. Since then, the whole project has reached a standstill. Covid-19 has been mentioned as a reason (Ggrasia, 2022). However, Chow's company's financial difficulties have been the major cause of this lack of progress (CLBrief, 2022). Cape Verde government gave Macau Legend until the end of 2022 to provide information on the schedule of the project's execution, to no avail. In January 2023, Cape Verde Prime Minister, Ulisses Correia e Silva, declared the project 'untenable' (Macau New, 2023).

It therefore remains to be seen if this project gets completed and stays in the hands of the Macau Legend Company. For the time-being, the only Cape Verde casino in operation is located on Sal Island and is owned by the Senator Group whose headquarters are in the United Kingdom.

In any event, although the Cape Verdean government is likely to have received help and advice from the US administration, this story illustrates how much agency this country has been able to keep, to better protect its financial interests.

Cape Verde's economic proximity with Europe

Despite its growing presence, China has been unable to change the basic features of Cape Verde's external economic relations. These have remained, on the whole, turned towards the European Union, both in terms of foreign direct investment (FDI) and trade.

In the last few years, Chinese FDIs in Cape Verde have increased, to reach 16% of the total flow in 2018 (1,675.6 million Escudos or around 160 million Euros), more than Portugal's (13.6%) and not much less than Spain (20%). Nonetheless, in 2020 Chinese FDIs dropped to 3% (215.8 Escudos or 20 million Euros) of the total, against 20% for Portugal and 17.6% for Spain. Spain, Portugal and the United Kingdom have remained the main origins of FDIs to Cape Verde (Banco de Cabo Verde, 2022). And the EU is still today its main investor, Spain representing in 2021 57% of total EU FDIs in Cape Verde, Portugal 25%, Italy 18% and France 5% (Mapping EU Investment, 2022).

The same picture emerges in Cape Verde's foreign trade. China is today Cape

Verde's third trade partner, behind the EU and Argentina and ahead of the United States: 60 million Euros in 2021 (5.7% of the total), against 719 million (67%), 93 million (8.9%) and 41 million (3.9%) respectively. According to figures published, China-Cape Verde bilateral trade amounted to US\$86 million. But China does not import any products from this country, in contrast with the EU (49 million Euros) or even the US (3 million Euros) which buy fish. In any event, Cape Verde trade is very imbalanced, its exports representing less than 6% of its imports (European Commission, 2022).

Cape Verde has tried to attract Chinese tourists. In 2011, Cape Verde Embassy in Beijing delivered 700 visas, a number that has probably increased since then (Holmes, 2011).⁸ In any case, this is a small number compared to the number of tourists arriving, mainly from Europe, every year – more than the entire population of the archipelago (567,000 in 2019). Chinese tour operators estimated in 2017 that up to 100,000 Chinese tourists could visit the country if facilities were improved (Nault, 2017). Nonetheless, prior to Covid, despite the possibility for Chinese nationals to obtain a visa on arrival, the number of Chinese tourists remained very low.

More generally, since 2007 Cape Verde's 'special partnership' with the EU has remained crucial for this country since it has not only been aimed at stimulating trade and investment but also stemming the major security challenges it faces: illicit migration, drug-trafficking and organised crime. This partnership has been consolidated by a 'constant political dialogue' and in 2017 cooperation was expanded to other sectors such as ocean governance and the blue economy (Delegation of the European Union to Cabo Verde, 2021a; Interview 9).

Cape Verde's international military cooperation

The same can be said of Cape Verde's international military cooperation. Apart from the projects mentioned above, as elsewhere in Africa, every year China offers short-term training (generally six months) in China to a small number of Cape Verdean officers. It has also supplied this country's national guard communication equipment. Since the early 2010s, military cooperation between the two countries has developed. But it has remained by and large modest, and way behind any agreement between Cape Verde and the United States or Portugal.

In 2011, China delivered another two multi-role Harbin Z-9s to Cape Verde for both military and civilian use (apparently the Harbin Z-9 delivered in 1994 is no longer on the inventory) (All-Time Aircraft Used List, no date; Military of Cape Verde, no date). Two years later, China announced that it would give Cape Verde US\$50 million, described by the local press as a donation, to fund the construction

⁸ However, no more recent data are available.

of a unit making uniforms for the armed forces and the purchase of two coastguard patrol boats (Cabo Verde, Politics, 2013). In 2017, Cape Verde's Minister of Defence, Luís Filipe Tavares, travelled to Beijing. Three years later, on 12 March 2020, both countries signed a 'protocol for free military assistance' amounting to \$5 million (4.4 million Euros) over five years, including supply of military hardware, mainly modern radios, trucks and buses, as well as training (Permanent Secretariat, 2020; Lusa, 2020).

More intriguing has been some information made public around the same time, according to which, Cape Verde officers were among the African officers (together with South African, Mozambican, etc.) who attended PLA's political schools in China, where its own model of ruling party's absolute control of the military was promoted. Of course, this model is more adaptable to nations like Zimbabwe or Rwanda than multi-party democracies such as Cape Verde or South Africa. Nonetheless, this type of training highlights Beijing's ambition to export key features of its political model to Africa (Nantulya, 2020).

Yet, Cape Verde's security relationship with the US and Portugal has remained stronger and closer. In 2010, a US-funded US\$3 million Maritime Security Centre – only the second in Africa – was opened in Praia, highlighting both the strategic location of this country but also the US strong interest in it. A year later, the US Africa Command (Africom) signed a US\$200,000 co-operation agreement with the Cape Verdean armed forces to pay for equipment for coastguard patrol vessels. This has helped the fight against drug trafficking in the area (Cook and Husted, 2017, pp.8-9).

In addition, US Navy and Coast Guard ships have been making frequent visits to the islands. In 2017, the US State Department listed Cape Verde among its African 'anchor states'; and in 2017, the two nations signed a Status of Forces Agreement to specify the legal conditions under which American troops would enter the country (Lilyblad, 2020). In 2018, Africom hosted its annual conference in Cape Verde. A few months later, in March 2019, the US State Department pushed for an increased security collaboration with this country, especially in addressing its most pressing threats: crime, trafficking and terrorism (Hill, 2021). The same year, Cape Verde announced its intention to establish a 'strategic alliance' with NATO, with the aim to 'guarantee more and better security' for the archipelago and in particular for its vast maritime space. More recently, to deepen their security relationship, in December 2022, the US Department of Defence and the Ministry of Defence of Cape Verde signed a Memorandum of Understanding on Defence Cooperation (U.S. Department of Defense, 2022). Cape Verde's close defence partners include Portugal, its former colonizer, which trains some of Cape Verde's officers and is helping the nation to conclude its rapprochement with NATO. Finally, in 2019, Cape Verde agreed to host an international military training centre,

partly controlled by Competences – a Cape Verdean private security firm, and partly by Nibor Enterprises – a US and Israeli engineering and general contractor company (Africa Defense Forum, 2019). Called Orbit Training Centre, and opened a year later, this centre trains local military as well as potential peacekeepers. Its personnel is largely European (Orbit Training Centre, no date).

China's cultural offensive and its limits

On the cultural front, especially since the launching of the BRI, China has also been on the offensive. In 2015, its ambassador in Cape Verde managed to convince the local authorities to let a Confucius Institute open its doors. First located in the Institut Français (French Institute) building on Plato, in downtown Praia, it subsequently moved to New University Campus in 2022. This institute has three Chinese teachers, including two volunteers, all from Guangdong University of Foreign Studies. It claims to have trained, by 2022, 5,000 students. In 2017, the Confucius Institute signed an agreement with Cape Verde's Ministry of Education to start teaching Chinese in the country's middle schools. No opposition to this initiative has been reported as Cape Verde, as most African countries, had never before offered any Chinese language training, either for lack of funds or interest. In addition to the construction of a New University Campus, the Chinese government has also offered a growing number of scholarships (350 scholarships by 2020 against 100 in 2007) (Horta, 2008; *Waijiaobu*, 2022).

Nevertheless, these cultural relations have remained much weaker than the cultural relations that Cape Verde has not only kept with other Lusophone countries but also developed with Europe and Northern America. The large Cape Verde diaspora in these two parts of the world as well as the flow of tourists from the EU and Britain have contributed to enhancing these cultural links.

China's Covid-19 diplomacy and its limits

Very early on, as part of its charm offensive in the Global South, particularly in Africa, China has donated masks, personal protection equipment and anti-Covid-19 vaccines to Cape Verde. However, it is far from having been the only one. While it gave 50,000 Sinopharm doses, this was a small proportion of the total that Cape Verde received: 715,150 doses, including 161,150 from the COVAX Facility and 554,000 from bilateral deals and donations by the end of November 2021. The other donors included the United States (487,190 doses donated in partnership with Covax), the EU and some of its member states (565,050), such as France (30,000), Hungary (100,000, with the help of the local Catholic Church), and Portugal (24,000) (U.S. Department of State, 2022; Delegation of the European Union to Cabo Verde, 2021b). In addition, the Cape Verdean government bought 250,000 vaccines thanks to a \$5 million concessional loan from the World Bank (Interview 6).

It should be noted that Cape Verde has not suffered as much as other countries from the pandemic. By 14 February 2023, it had only 63,235 confirmed cases and 413 deaths. Two thirds (more than 300,000) of its population has been fully vaccinated (WHO, 2023).

US push-back against China's growing footprint

The US is openly worried about China's growing influence in Cape Verde. In October 2020, in his confirmation hearing, Assistant Secretary of Defence for Strategy, Plans and Capabilities, Victor Mercado, declared: 'We know China is very interested in Africa. Not only in the base they established in Djibouti, but we know they're interested in the west side, like Cape Verde, Equatorial Guinea'. However, the US is clearly giving more attention to Cape Verde. In February 2021, while congratulating Cape Verde for its selection for the US National Guard State Partnership Programme, Anthony Blinken called Cape Verde Foreign Affairs and Defence Minister Rui Figueiredo with a clear objective: 'Advance shared priorities, expand commercial relations, and strengthen our security partnership' (U.S. Embassy in Cabo Verde, 2021).

A few months later, the American government announced plans to invest half-a-billion dollars in Cape Verde, US\$400 million of the package being used to build a new Embassy in Praia just behind the seat of the Cape Verde government, built with assistance from China. Its personnel will reach 300 local and diplomatic staff (Hill, 2021). Located on the plateau, the old US Embassy is today way too small, especially compared to the Chinese representation.

An interesting anecdote can also illustrate the US push-back: it is said that the municipality of Praia deliberately gave the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints a large space on which to build a temple, next to the National Library built by China and the square with Amilcar Cabral's statue gifted by China, in order to prevent Chinese companies and interests, which had built a mall on the other side of this long perimeter, from getting control of the whole area (Interview 1). Started in 2018, along the Avenida Cidade de Lisboa, the Mormon temple was completed in May 2022. The number of Mormons in Cape Verde increased from 25 in 1989 to around 16,000 in 2019 (Temples of the Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-Day Saints, no date).

Conclusion

There is no question that China's footprint in Cape Verde has steadily increased since the early 2000s and even more since the launching of the BRI. As elsewhere in Africa, its presence has been mostly felt in the infrastructure and the health sectors. Yet, China's active involvement in the Cape Verdean government's

communication system, with the help of Huawei, its contribution to São Vicente Maritime SEZ, its decision to open a Confucius Institute, and its assistance in the construction of the National University's new campus, have all strengthened its influence in this country. Often filling a vacuum due to a lack of interest from other countries, the Chinese government has made attractive offers, a *modus operandi* that has been observed in other small island states close to the African continent, such as Seychelles (Cabestan, 2021).

Nonetheless, China is not a major trade partner of, nor a large investor in, Cape Verde. Its military cooperation programmes are close to symbolic and its cultural influence minimal. Moreover, Macau Forum's role has remained marginal or rather negative, in the case of the half-failed casino project. In other words, China's presence is not as important as in other African countries.

This contrasted picture has probably helped Cape Verde keep a meaningful agency in its relationship with China. On the one hand, developing relations with China – and also with Brazil and Angola – has been part of Cape Verde's effort to diversify its external relations and reduce its dependence upon the European Union (Cook and Husted, 20167, p.4). On the other hand, as we have seen, Praia has been able to turn down some of China's most controversial projects, such as David Chow's bank. But other factors have played a role. As with Djibouti or Seychelles (Cabestan, 2020; Cabestan, 2021), Cape Verde's strategic geographic location as well as China's growing activism have stimulated the US or the EU's interest in this country. Its large diaspora in both places has been another powerful force of connectivity and interaction. Its proximity to the European continent and close relationship with Portugal, its former colonizer, also explain why the EU continues to loom large in Cape Verde.

China has made significant political and economic inroads in Cape Verde to the point that it is now hard for this country, because of the structural asymmetry of their relationship, to antagonize China in the United Nations or ECOWAS (Economic Community of West African States). This is a clear limit to small island states' agency vis-à-vis great powers, perceptible in other countries such as Seychelles or Comoros. Yet, it has been possible for Cape Verde to maintain a balance between its three major partners, the EU, USA and China, since it is actively courted by each of them. Here again, short of the Indian factor which is totally absent in Cape Verde, similarities with Seychelles are worth noting.

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Interviews

Interview 1: João Paulo Madeira, Professor of Social Sciences, University of Cabo Verde.

Interview 2: Chinese residents in Cape Verde.

Interview 3: Huawei cadre.

Interview 4: Honorary Consul of a European country in Cape Verde.

Interview 5: Executive of São Vicente Maritime Special Economic Zone.

Interview 6: CABNAVE Executive.

Interview 7: Western diplomat in Cape Verde.

Interview 8: Longxin cadre.

Interview 9: European Union diplomat in Cape Verde.

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